

IMPROVISATION IN THE PROCESS OF SPEAKING

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Abstract: This article provides information on the concepts of language, speech and improvisation. Thoughts on the effective use of improvisation and excellent learning in the process of speaking are described.

Key words: Language, speech, improvisation, word, vocabulary skill, ability, skill, spirituality, public explanation, national identity

“The language and literature of every nation’s life show its presence in the world. To lose the national language is to lose the soul of the nation”.

Abdulla Avloni

The role of the mother tongue is important in the spiritual development of a person, in the cultural and educational development of his society. Our mother tongue is another spirit that unites nations, educates them, preserves customs, traditions and cultures, ensures that they are passed from generation to generation, and makes everyone feel the sign of love in their hearts. Alisher Navoi, the sultan of the word property, said, “The lock of the heart is the lock of the heart, and the key of the heart is the word, that is, the key to the treasure of the human heart is the word”, focused on. The centuries-old rich history of our people, the ancient and colorful culture was formed under the influence of the Uzbek language. Our great poet Alisher Navoi created priceless works in this language and amazed the world. In this language, our mother tongue sounds and is developing.

If a gardener cultivates and cares for his crops with manual labor, a teacher becomes a mature expert of his profession with his rich speech and language. Some teachers who speak little and have very poor speech skills may find it difficult and boring to spend even 45 minutes in the teaching process, as well as need a certain amount of time to prepare. The richness and vividness of the speech is a sign that the teacher is intelligent and intelligent, who can love his profession and justify it.

Speech is the use of language in the processes of expression and exchange of ideas, a certain way of life of language as a separate type of social activity. Speech refers to the processes of its oral (voice) and written manifestation, that is, the process of speaking and its result - speech ideas and works that are stored in memory or recorded in writing.¹

In addition to the communication-intervention function, speech can perform other functions, such as a poetic function. A special form of speech is reading. Each person's speech is individual and has its own characteristics; However, the main elements of the language - vocabulary and grammatical structure do not belong only to individuals, but are general, that is, they apply to a specific language community. Speech is closely related to a person's thinking, his consciousness. A person's thoughts are formed and exist in speech. Thanks to speech and on the basis of speech, it becomes possible to abstractly reflect the existence in a general way, to think logically, which goes beyond the scope of individuality and becomes a product of society. Speech is of great importance in other aspects of a person's psyche, in his intuition, perception, memory, thoughts, feelings, will, in the manifestation and actions of others, in the development of a person's consciousness. In any form and in any case, clarity, fluency, simplicity, impressiveness should remain the most important features of speech.

Improvisation (lat. *improvisus* - unexpected, accidental) - creation of poetry, music and a certain work during the performance without prior preparation;

¹ Abduvahob Mavdaliyev O'ZME birinchi jild. Toshkent 2000-yil.

inspiration, creative fantasy, spiritual upliftment, freedom of thought, words, tone and image that arise spontaneously in an actor's game.² That is, the method of unprepared explanation, the teacher asks the students a question or task and asks them to explain the answer without preparation. The advantages of this method are that students have their own personal thoughts and worldviews, develop their oral speech, develop the ability to frequently analyze each question and assignment in memory, develop thinking skills, learns to use application skills. Improvisation in an actor's game enlivens the role being performed, gives it a new meaning. Improvisation played a key role in the performances of the actors of the ancient folk theater - skomoroks, mimes, clowns and entertainers, especially the actors of the Italian folk comedy theater ("Del Arte"). Improvisation played an important role in the work of Uzbek actors like Soyib Khojayev and Gani Azamov.

In the process of speaking, improvisation is very high in some people, and in others it is not formed. People who are afraid to express their thoughts in the process of improvisation will carry out this process slowly, and this indicates that their speech will be ineffective and boring. In the process of speaking, a person who believes in his thinking ability without paying attention to any external words, this process is very reliable and effective. Also, to overcome the fear that appears before public speaking and to stop all excitement, some recommend preparing in front of the mirror and imagining success. But most of these tips are useless and have side effects. Many people pay attention to themselves in the process of speaking, but the sentences that are thought and used in the process of speaking are neglected. Above all, do not focus on yourself, but rather on the beauty of your speech and how well you use words correctly and appropriately. First of all, you need to understand that the nervousness before speaking in front of hundreds or even thousands of people is not the speaking itself, but the fear of public humiliation. And you worry and fear what people think about you. As a result of this fear, you cannot fully express yourself. The success of your speech is not

² O'zME. Birinchi jild. Toshkent, 2000-yil

dependent on what people think of you. In this case, it is important how accurately and clearly you convey your thoughts to the audience, as well as through a beautiful speech. The audience must understand the main idea of your speech and its meaning. The best way to do this is to think and express ideas in a broader way than in regular conversations. To do this, you need to focus more on your ideas and how well your speech can convey the idea, rather than on yourself. At the end of your speech, people may think you are angry, nervous, honest, innocent, bold, or polite. But if you have not been able to convey your thoughts to them, then the task set before you has not been completed and you will be unable to convey your thoughts. If you learn to overcome your fear, you will be prepared for any improvisational situation during the speech process. It's useless to watch yourself and take videos of how you look. When we do not do this process, we pay too much attention to ourselves, we should pay attention not to ourselves, but to our speech and to what extent it is fully expressed. Focusing not on yourself, but on what you want to say and what you can convey to your audience will take away most of your anxiety, and you will become a better speaker and achieve your goals. Then you will become less hesitant and able to overcome fear. Your main task is what you send, the information you leave, and the listeners are the receivers. It's up to you how well you can deliver to your audience, how well you can deliver your speech, and how well you can deliver the right information. If you learn to identify, refine, develop, and communicate your ideas, you will surely succeed.

In conclusion, our noble aspirations and efforts aimed at establishing New Uzbekistan within the framework of the Development Strategy are reaching a decisive stage. In this way, our mother tongue, which is a symbol of our national identity and pride, serves as an incomparable source of strength and inspiration. It is the civic duty of all of us to fundamentally increase the prestige of our native language in the social life of our people and at the international level, to educate the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism, loyalty to national traditions and values and to fully apply the state language to life.

Also, any situations of improvisation in speaking indicate that you will be able to overcome fear and excitement, and your skills in using words in relation to your profession will increase even more in the future. True happiness is in our strong faith! The strength of our faith is in the beauty of our language.

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